

Labeo seeberi Clanwilliam sandfish

© J. Shelton

Group: Bony fish

Size: Max length is 35.5 cm SL

Distribution:

Endemic to South Africa within the drainage basin of the Olifants–Doring River System.

Importance:

The Clanwilliam sandfish is endemic to South Africa and is one of South Africa's most threatened migratory freshwater fish. It is listed as Endangered on the IUCN list of species. It was once widespread throughout the Olifants–Doring River system but has disappeared from many of these waterways due to pollution and impacts by invasive species.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 41.64 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 1.88 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.92 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 65.5% [Single: 63.1%, Duplicated: 2.4%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 13.15 kilobases

Contig number: 108 194

Sample Contributor contact details:

Gwynneth Matcher

South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity

g.matcher@saiab.nrf.ac.za